

Some Properties of Quasiclaw-Free Graphs

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Abstract

In this paper, the terminology and notations of the graph theory are stated as an introduction. Among the so many interesting things of the graph theory, the claw, the claw-free and the quasi claw-free graphs are studied from the theoretical point of view. Mainly the properties of quasi claw-free graphs are discussed.

Key word: induced subgraph, neighbors, claw, claw-free, quasi claw-free.

1. Introduction to Graph Theory

The following definitions and notations are from (J.A. Bondy, U.S.R. Murty, *Graph Theory with Applications*, Fifth Printing, American Elsevier, New York, 1982.)

A **graph** G is an ordered triple $(V(G), E(G), \psi_G)$ consisting of a nonempty set $V(G)$ of **vertices**, a set $E(G)$, disjoint from $V(G)$, of **edges**, and an **incidence function** ψ_G that associates with each edge of G an unordered pair of vertices of (not necessarily distinct) G . If e is an edge and u and v are vertices such that $\psi_G(e) = uv$, then e is said to **join** u and v ; the vertices u and v are called the **ends** of e . The ends of an edge are said to be **incident** with the edge. Two vertices which are incident with a common edge are **adjacent**; as are two edges which are incident with a common vertex. An edge with identical ends is called a **loop**. A graph is **finite** if both its vertex set and edge set are finite. We use the symbols $|V(G)|$ and $|E(G)|$ to denote the numbers of vertices and edges in graph G . Two graphs G and H are said to be **isomorphic** (written $G \cong H$) if there are bijections $\theta: V(G) \rightarrow V(H)$ and $\phi: E(G) \rightarrow E(H)$ such that $\psi_G(e) = uv$ if and only if $\psi_H(\phi(e)) = \theta(u)\theta(v)$; such pair (θ, ϕ) of mappings is called an **isomorphism** between G and H . A graph is called a **simple** graph if it has no loops and no two of its links join the same pair of vertices. A simple graph in which each pair of distinct vertices is joined by an edge is called a **complete graph**. There is one complete graph on n vertices; it is denoted by K_n . A **bipartite graph** is one whose vertex set can be partitioned into two subsets X and Y , so that each edge has one end in X and one end in Y ; such a partition (X, Y) is called a **bipartition** of the graph. A **complete bipartite** graph is a simple bipartite graph with bipartition (X, Y) in which each vertex of X is joined to each vertex of Y ; if $|X| = m$ and $|Y| = n$, such a graph is denoted by $K_{m,n}$. A graph H is a **subgraph** of G (written $H \subseteq G$) if $V(H) \subseteq V(G)$, $E(H) \subseteq E(G)$ and ψ_H is the restriction of ψ_G to $E(H)$. When $H \subseteq G$ but $H \neq G$, we write $H \subset G$ and call H a **proper subgraph** of G . The **degree** $d(v)$ of a vertex v in G is the number of edges of G incident with v , each loop counting as two edges. The **order** of a graph G is the number of vertices in G . The **size** of a graph G is the number of edges in G . Suppose that S is a nonempty subset of V . The subgraph of G whose vertex set is S and whose edge set is the set of those edges of G that have both ends in S is called the subgraph of G **induced by** S and is denoted by $\langle S \rangle$; we say that $\langle S \rangle$ is an **induced subgraph** of G . If vertices u and v are connected in G , the **distance** between u and v in G , denoted by $d(u, v)$, is the length of a shortest (u, v) -path in G . Adjacent vertices are said to be neighbors. A subset S of V is called an **independent set** of G if any two vertices in S are nonadjacent.

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2. Some Concepts of Quasi Claw-Free Graphs

In this section, we study some definitions such as H -free, claw, claw-free, neighborhoods of a vertex and quasi claw-free graphs, and state some concepts of them.

2.1 Definition. If H is a graph, then we say that graph G is **H -free** if G does not contain a copy of H as an induced subgraph.

2.2 Definition. The **claw** graph is an induced subgraph of a graph G which is isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$.

2.3 Example. The following graph is claw graph.

Fig.1

2.4 Definition. A graph G is said to be **claw-free** if it does not contain an induced subgraph that is isomorphic to claw.

2.5 Example. Consider the following graph G with $V = \{a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h\}$. Let $V' = \{a, h, e, g\}$, $V'' = \{a, b, h, d\}$ where V' and V'' are subsets of V . Then $\langle V' \rangle$ and $\langle V'' \rangle$ are isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$. Therefore G is not a claw-free graph.

Fig.2

2.6 Examples. The following graphs are claw-free graphs.

Fig.3

2.7 Definition. The *inflation* of any graph G is a graph which is obtained by replacing each vertex u by a complete graph $K_{d_G(u)}$ and joining each edge of G to a different vertex of $K_{d_G(u)}$.

2.8 Example.

Fig.4

The graph G' is the inflation of graph G .

2.9 Example. The inflation of a graph G is a claw-free graph.

2.10 Definition. For any set S of vertices in G , we define the *neighbor set* of S in G to be the set of all vertices adjacent to vertices in S ; this set is denoted by $N(S)$.

2.11 Definitions. The *neighborhood of a vertex* u , written $N(u)$, is the set of vertices adjacent to u .

The *open neighborhood* of u is denoted by $N(u) = \{x \in V \mid xu \in E\}$.

The *closed neighborhood* of u is denoted by $N[u] = \{u\} \cup N(u)$.

2.12 Example. Consider the following graph G , the vertex set is $\{u, v, w, x, y\}$ and the edge set is $\{uv, ux, uw, vx, vw, xw, xy\}$. Then we have $N(u) = \{v, w, x\}$ and $N[u] = \{u, v, w, x\}$.

Fig.5

2.13 Definition. For each pair (a, b) of vertices in G at distance 2, we define the set $J(a, b) = \{u \in N(a) \cap N(b) \mid N[u] \subseteq N[a] \cup N[b]\}$.

2.14 Definition. A graph G is *quasi claw-free* if every pair (x, y) of vertices at distance 2 satisfies the condition $J(x, y) \neq \emptyset$. We denote the classes of claw-free and quasi claw-free graphs by CF and QCF , respectively.

2.15 Example. The following graph G is quasi claw-free graph.

Fig.6

2.16 Example. Consider $V(G) = \{u, v, w, x, y\}$ and $E(G) = \{uv, ux, vw, xw, xy\}$. Then the following graph G is not quasi claw-free graph.

Fig.7

2.17 Definition. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph and an injection $f: V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ (where \mathbb{N} is the set of natural numbers). We define **the graph $G(f)$** as follows: to each vertex x of G we associate a complete graph $K_{f(x)}$ and we join each vertex of $K_{f(x)}$ to every vertex of $K_{f(y)}$ whenever $xy \in E(G)$. We note that if G is QCF then so does $G(f)$.

2.18 Example. Consider a graph $G = (V, E)$ where $V(G) = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $E(G) = \{ab, bc, cd\}$ and an injection $f: V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ (where \mathbb{N} is the set of natural numbers) defined by $f(a) = 1, f(b) = 2, f(c) = 3$ and $f(d) = 4$. Then we have $K_{f(a)} = K_1, K_{f(b)} = K_2, K_{f(c)} = K_3, K_{f(d)} = K_4$. Then the graph G and $G(f)$ are quasi claw-free graphs.

Fig.8

2.19 Proposition. For $r \geq 3$, let Q_r be the graph with vertex set $V_0 \cup V_1 \cup V_2$ and edge set $E_0 \cup E_1 \cup E_2$, where V_i, E_i ($0 \leq i \leq 2$) are defined as follows: $V_0 = \{0\}$, $V_1 = \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$, $V_2 = \{(i, j) \mid 1 \leq i < j \leq r\}$, $E_0 = \{0i \mid i \in V_1\}$, $E_1 = \{i(s, t) \mid i \in V_1, (s, t) \in V_2 \text{ and either } i = s \text{ or } i = t\}$ and $E_2 = \{(i, j)(s, t) \mid (i, j), (s, t) \in V_2 \text{ and } \{i, j\} \cap \{s, t\} \neq \emptyset\}$.

We have $d(0) = r, d(u) = 1 + (r - 1) = r$ if $u \in V_1$, and $d(u) = 2 + \left[\binom{r}{2} - 1 - \binom{r-2}{2} \right] = 2(r-1)$

if $u \in V_2$. Then Q_r is a quasi claw-free graph of order $1 + r + \binom{r}{2}$.

Proof. Take any two vertices u and v in Q_r such that $d(u, v) = 2$.

Case (i)

$0 \in V_0$ and $v \in V_2$.

Let $v = (i, j), 1 \leq i < j \leq r$.

Since a vertex 0 in V_0 is adjacent to every vertex in V_1 and not adjacent to every vertex in V_2 , we have

$$N(0) = \{1, \dots, r\} = V_1, N(v) = \{s \mid s \in V_1, s=i \text{ or } s=j\} \cup \{(s,t) \mid (s,t) \in V_2, \{i,j\} \cap \{s,t\} \neq \emptyset\}.$$

$$N[0] \cap N[v] = \{s \mid s \in V_1, \text{ either } s=i \text{ or } s=j\}.$$

Therefore $i, j \in N(0) \cap N(v)$.

$$N[i] = V_0 \cup \{i \in V_1\} \cup \{(s,t) \mid (s,t) \in V_2, \text{ either } s=i \text{ or } t=i\}.$$

$$N[j] = V_0 \cup \{j \in V_1\} \cup \{(s,t) \mid (s,t) \in V_2, \text{ either } s=j \text{ or } t=j\}.$$

$$N[0] = \{0\} \cup V_1.$$

$$N[v] = \{(i,j)\} \cup \{s \mid s \in V_1, s=i \text{ or } s=j\} \cup \{(s,t) \mid (s,t) \in V_2, \{i,j\} \cap \{s,t\} \neq \emptyset\}.$$

$$N[0] \cup N[v] = V_0 \cup V_1 \cup \{(i,j) \in V_2\} \cup \{s \mid s \in V_1, s=i \text{ or } s=j\} \cup \{(s,t) \mid (s,t) \in V_2, \{i,j\} \cap \{s,t\} \neq \emptyset\}.$$

Hence $N[i] \subseteq N[0] \cup N[v]$ and $N[j] \subseteq N[0] \cup N[v]$.

Therefore $J(u, v) = \{i, j\} \neq \emptyset$.

Case (ii)

$u \in V_1$ and $v \in V_1$ where $u \neq v$.

Since every vertices in V_1 is adjacent to every vertices in V_2 but not adjacent to every vertices in V_1 , we have $N(u) = V_0 \cup \{(i, j) \mid (i, j) \in V_2, \text{ either } u = i \text{ or } u = j\}$,

$$N(v) = V_0 \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \text{ either } v = s \text{ or } v = t\}.$$

$$N(u) \cap N(v) = V_0 \cup \{(u, v) \in V_2\} = \{0, (u, v)\}.$$

$$N[0] = V_1 \cup V_0.$$

$$N[(u, v)] = \{s \mid s \in V_1, s = u \text{ or } s = v\} \cup \{(u, v) \in V_2\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \{u, v\} \cap \{s, t\} \neq \emptyset\}.$$

$$N[u] \cup N[v] = V_0 \cup \{u\} \cup \{(i, j) \mid (i, j) \in V_2, \text{ either } u = i \text{ or } u = j\} \cup \{v\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \text{ either } v = s \text{ or } v = t\}.$$

Hence $N[0] \subseteq N[u] \cup N[v]$ and $N[(u, v)] \subseteq N[u] \cup N[v]$.

Therefore $J(u, v) = \{(u, v)\} \neq \emptyset$.

Case (iii)

$u \in V_1$ and $v \in V_2$ where $u \neq i$ and $u \neq j$. Let $v = (i, j)$, $1 \leq i < j \leq r$.

$N(u) = V_0 \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \text{ either } s = u \text{ or } t = u\}$.

$N(v) = \{i, j\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \{i, j\} \cap \{s, t\} \neq \emptyset\}$.

$N(u) \cap N(v) = \{(i, u), (u, j)\}$.

$N[(i, u)] = \{i, u\} \cup \{(i, u)\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \{i, u\} \cap \{s, t\} \neq \emptyset\}$.

$N[(u, j)] = \{u, j\} \cup \{(u, j)\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \{u, j\} \cap \{s, t\} \neq \emptyset\}$.

$N[u] \cup N[v] = V_0 \cup \{u\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \text{ either } s = u \text{ or } t = u\} \cup \{v\} \cup \{(s, t) \mid (s, t) \in V_2, \{i, j\} \cap \{s, t\} \neq \emptyset\}$.

Therefore $N[(u, j)] \subseteq N[u] \cup N[v]$ and $N[(i, u)] \subseteq N[u] \cup N[v]$.

Hence $J(u, v) = \{(i, u), (u, j)\} \neq \emptyset$.

Case (iv)

$u \in V_2$ and $v \in V_2$ where $u \neq v$.

Let $u = (i, j)$, and $v = (s, t)$, $1 \leq i < j \leq r$, $1 \leq s < t \leq r$.

$N(u) = \{i, j\} \cup \{(i, s), (i, t), (j, s), (j, t)\}$.

$N(v) = \{s, t\} \cup \{(i, s), (i, t), (j, s), (j, t)\}$.

$N(u) \cap N(v) = \{(i, s), (i, t), (j, s), (j, t)\}$.

$N[u] \cup N[v] = \{(i, j), (s, t)\} \cup \{i, j, s, t\} \cup \{(i, s), (i, t), (j, s), (j, t)\}$.

$N[(i, s)] = \{i, s\} \cup \{(i, s)\} \cup \{(i, j), (i, t), (j, s), (s, t)\}$.

$N[(i, t)] = \{i, t\} \cup \{(i, t)\} \cup \{(i, j), (i, s), (j, t), (s, t)\}$.

$N[(j, s)] = \{j, s\} \cup \{(j, s)\} \cup \{(i, j), (i, s), (j, t), (s, t)\}$.

$N[(j, t)] = \{j, t\} \cup \{(j, t)\} \cup \{(i, j), (i, t), (j, s), (s, t)\}$.

$N[(i, s)], N[(i, t)], N[(j, s)]$ and $N[(j, t)]$ are subsets of $N[u] \cup N[v]$.

Therefore $J(u, v) = \{(i, s), (i, t), (j, s), (j, t)\} \neq \emptyset$.

From the four cases, we have $J(u, v) \neq \emptyset$.

So Q_r is a quasi claw-free graph.

2.20 Example. The following figure depicts the graph Q_4 .

Fig.9

2.21 Definition. The *strong product* of graphs G and H is a graph $G \cdot H$ with vertex set $V(G) \times V(H)$, in which (u,v) is adjacent to (u',v') if and only if either $u = u'$ and $vv' \in E(H)$, or $v = v'$ and $uu' \in E(G)$, or $uu' \in E(G)$ and $vv' \in E(H)$.

3. Properties of Quasi Claw-Free Graphs

Some properties of the quasi claw-free graphs referring to (A. Ainouche, Quasi claw-free graphs, *Discrete Math.* **179** (1998) 13-26.) are discussed in this section.

3.1 Theorem. Every claw-free graph is quasi claw-free.

Proof. Suppose that a graph G is not a quasi claw-free graph.

Then $J(a, b) = \{u \in N(a) \cap N(b) \mid N[u] \subseteq N[a] \cup N[b]\} = \emptyset$, where $d(a, b) = 2$.

This means that $N[u]$ is not subset of the union of $N[a]$ and $N[b]$.

Then there is a vertex in $N[u]$, say x , such that $x \notin N[a] \cup N[b]$.

So x is adjacent to u and not adjacent to a and b .

But u is adjacent to a and b because $u \in N(a) \cap N(b)$.

Since u is adjacent to x, a and b which are not adjacent, we have an induced subgraph of G which is isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$.

So G is not a claw-free graph.

Hence if G is claw-free, G is quasi claw-free graph.

So every claw-free graphs is quasi claw-free graph.

3.2 Theorem. The strong product $G \cdot K_2$ of a quasi claw-free graph G is quasi claw-free.

Proof. Suppose that G is a quasi claw-free graph.

Let $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ and $V(K_2) = \{x, y\}$.

Then $V(G) \times V(K_2) = \{(v_1, x), (v_1, y), (v_2, x), (v_2, y), \dots, (v_n, x), (v_n, y)\}$.

Take any (v_i, x) and (v_j, y) in $G \cdot K_2$ where $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$, $1 \leq i, j \leq n$ and x and y are any vertex in $V(K_2)$.

Since $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$, there exists at least one vertex pair (v_k, w) which is adjacent to (v_i, x) and (v_j, y) where $w = x$ or $w = y$ but (v_i, x) and (v_j, y) are not adjacent.

It follows that we have the following cases.

Case (i)

$v_i = v_j$ and $xy \notin E(K_2)$.

Then we have $x = y$ because if $x \neq y$, $x, y \in K_2$ then $xy \in E(K_2)$.

Thus $(v_i, x) = (v_j, y)$ which is impossible because $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$.

Case (ii)

$v_i \neq v_j$ and $xy \in E(K_2)$.

By the definition of strong product, we have $v_i v_j \notin E(G)$.

Since $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$ and $v_i v_j \notin E(G)$, there exists at least one vertex which is adjacent to v_i and v_j .

Therefore $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

Case (iii)

$v_i v_j \in E(G)$ and $x \neq y$.

Then we have $xy \in E(K_2)$.

By the definition of strong product, (v_i, x) is adjacent to (v_j, y) .

Thus $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 1$ which is impossible.

Case (iv)

$v_i v_j \notin E(G)$ and $x = y$

It follows that we have $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

Case (v)

$v_i v_j \in E(G)$ and $xy \notin E(K_2)$.

Then we have $x = y$.

By the definition of strong product, (v_i, x) is adjacent to (v_j, y) .

It follows that we have $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 1$ which is impossible.

Case (vi)

$v_i v_j \notin E(G)$ and $xy \in E(K_2)$.

Since $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$, there exists at least one vertex which is adjacent to v_i and v_j .

Therefore $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

Case (vii)

$v_i v_j \notin E(G)$ and $xy \notin E(K_2)$.

Then we have $x = y$.

Since $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$, $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

From the cases(ii),(iv),(vi)and(vii), we have $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

Since G is a quasi claw-free graph, $J(v_i, v_j) \neq \emptyset$ where $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

i.e., $J(v_i, v_j) = \{v_k \in N(v_i) \cap N(v_j) \mid N[v_k] \subseteq N[v_i] \cup N[v_j]\} \neq \emptyset$ where $d(v_i, v_j) = 2$.

Since (v_k, w) is adjacent to (v_i, x) and (v_j, y) ,

we have $(v_k, w) \in N((v_i, x)) \cap N((v_j, y))$.

If $w = x$ or $w = y$ then $N[w] = N[x]$ or $N[w] = N[y]$.

Since $N[v_k] \subseteq N[v_i] \cup N[v_j]$ and $N[x] = N[y] = N[w]$ where $x, y \in K_2$, we have

$N[(v_k, w)] \subseteq N[(v_i, x)] \cup N[(v_j, y)]$.

This means that $(v_k, w) \in J((v_i, x), (v_j, y))$ and $J((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) \neq \emptyset$ where $d((v_i, x), (v_j, y)) = 2$.

Therefore $G.K_2$ is quasi claw-free graph.

3.3 Theorem. A connected quasi claw-free graph with maximum degree at least 3 contains a triangle.

Proof. Let G be a quasi claw-free graph with $\Delta(G) \geq 3$.

Assume that G is triangle-free.

We observe that $z \in J(x, y)$ implies that $d(z) = 2$.

i.e., $z \in N(x) \cap N(y)$.

Choose a vertex a such that $d(a) \geq 3$ with three neighbors u, v, w .

These neighbors form an independent set for otherwise there is nothing more to prove.

Let $b \in J(u, v)$.

Clearly $b \neq a, w$ and $ab \notin E$.

Since $d(a, b) = 2$ we may assume, without loss of generality, $u \in J(a, b)$.

Considering $J(u, w)$ then yields an immediate contradiction since $J(u, w) \neq \emptyset$, $a, b \notin J(u, w)$ and $d(u) = 2$.

3.4 Proposition. A quasi claw-free graph is not necessarily $K_{1,r}$ -free with $r \geq 3$.

Proof. Consider a quasi claw-free Q_r graph with $r \geq 3$.

Since a vertex 0 in V_0 is adjacent to every vertex in V_1 and not adjacent to every vertex in V_2 but every vertex in V_1 is not adjacent to any vertex in its set, we have an induced subgraph $\langle V' \rangle$ where $V' = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, r\} \subseteq V$.

The induced subgraph V' of Q_r is isomorphic to $K_{1,r}$. Therefore Q_r is not $K_{1,r}$ -free.

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